

MeOH-H₂O, CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O-NH₄OH and CHCl₃-EtOAc-Me₂CO-MeOH-HOAc-H₂O for varying time periods (15-60 min). Out of these only the last two solvent systems, both with a 40 min development time, showed good separation. In the last named solvent system (60 : 12 : 15 : 16 : 3 : 3), PC and DGDG remained unresolved, although Mirayama and Morita⁴ reported that they had separated these under the same conditions. PC and DGDG could, however, be separated in the ammoniacal system (80 : 35 : 3 : 1), but in this system PE and MGDG coincided. Impregnation of the Chromarods either with oxalic acid (0.25 M in CH₃CN) or boric acid (1.2% in 1 : 1 aqueous EtOH) did not improve the resolution of the lipids.

In the plate tlc analysis, all the components of the mixture could be well separated using the acidic solvent system as stated above. In this system (visualisation by iodine vapour) the *R_f* values were : PC, 0.13 ; DGDG, 0.19 ; PE, 0.38 ; MGDG, 0.70. This was in fact better than the only other solvent system tried, viz. Me₂CO-MeC₆H₆-HOAc-H₂O (60 : 40 : 2 : 1), which was the best solvent system for galactolipids (*R_f* : MGDG, 0.11 ; DGDG, 0.05) but could not move the phospholipids. A similar observation had earlier been made by Goldschmidt⁵. Using double development technique, a separation of all the components could be achieved in Me₂CO-HOAc-H₂O (100 : 1 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH-HOAc-H₂O (25 : 15 : 4 : 2) on tlc plate, but the *R_f* values were closer, viz. PC, 0.26 ; DGDG, 0.30 ; PE, 0.57 and MGDG, 0.70. On the basis of our investigations, the application of both TLC and TLC/FID techniques using more than one solvent systems, seems to be a better approach for the separation of galactolipids from phospholipids.

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Ion-exchange Chromatographic Separation of Amino Acids on Impregnated Papers

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THE systematic applications of chromatographic methods made possible the quantitative separation, identification and estimation of amino acids in a

complex mixture with great speed, precision and sensitivity. These methods exploit differences in the solubility and acid-base behaviour of the different amino acids. The advantage of chromatography and ion-exchange can effectively be combined by the introduction of ion-exchange papers¹. The use of inorganic ion-exchangers as impregnating reagent, are preferred over their organic counterpart due to high selectivity and stability towards radiation and high temperature. The present communication describes the chromatographic behaviour and separation of few important amino acids on bismuth oxide impregnated paper using various aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed developing systems. Numerous physio-analytically important binary and ternary separations were achieved.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman no. 2 paper strips (18 × 3 cm) by ascending method. Chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade. The impregnation was performed as described in our earlier publication². The paper was conditioned for 15 min and the solvent was then allowed to ascend 15 cm in each case. The time required for the ascend of the aqueous and mixed developing solvent systems to a height of 15 cm was approximately 30-40 min.

A 0.2% solution of ninhydrin in n-butanol saturated with water was used as chromogenic agent for visualising the spots of amino acids on paper chromatograms. The *R_f* values were calculated as usual.

Chromatography : *R_f* values of the following 24 amino acids were calculated in 18 different aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed developing systems : glycine, DL-alanine, DL-2-amino-n-butyric acid, DL-serine, aspartic acid, L-glutamic acid, L-cysteine, L-cystine, DL-threonine, DL-methionine, DL-valine, L-leucine, DL-iso-leucine, DL-nor-leucine, L-lysine, L-arginine, L-ornithine, DL-β-phenylalanine, L-tyrosine, 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-DL-alanine, L-proline, L-hydroxyproline, L-histidine and DL-tryptophan. The various developing systems used were distilled water, 0.1 M aqueous sodium acetate and sodium potassium tartrate, methanol, ethanol, n-butanol, isobutanol, amyl alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, n-butanol saturated with water, n-butanol : acetic acid (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) and n-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 1 : 4, 5 : 2 : 3 and 5 : 4 : 1).

Separation : On the basis of appreciable difference in *R_f* values of amino acids, numerous binary and ternary separations were tried in different developing systems and some of the practically achieved physio-analytically important separations are as follow : (i) separation of L-glutamic acid (0.23) from aspartic acid (0.58) and L-arginine (0.11) from DL-methionine (0.57) in n-butanol saturated with water, (ii) separation of cystine (0.05) from cysteine (0.28), DL-serine (0.38) from DL-valine (0.66) and

DL-nor-leucine (0.45) from L-leucine (0.73) in n-butanol : acetic acid (1 : 1) ; (iii) separation of DL-serine (0.30) from L-proline (0.64), DOPA (0.26) from DL-valine (0.83) and DL-iso-leucine (0.55) from DL-nor-leucine (0.83) in n-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 4 : 1) as binary separations. Other separations achieved are L-cysteine (0.07) from DL-alanine (0.26) and glycine (0.40), L-arginine (0.12) from DL-alanine (0.26) and L-leucine (0.60) and DOPA (0.30) and DL-valine (0.48) in n-butanol saturated with water and separation of DL-serine (0.30) from L-lysine (0.50) and DL-tryptophan (0.67) and L-ornithine (0.31) from DL-valine (0.55) and DL-iso-leucine (0.76) in n-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 3 : 2) as ternary separations.

Results and Discussion

The results of chromatographic studies indicate that in aqueous and mixed developing systems amino acids show considerable movement while most of the nonpolar systems failed to effect the movement due to insolubility or low solubility of amino acids in these systems. The adsorption of amino acids by paper, however small, may also be one of the factors and can not be ignored completely³. It is observed that on bismuth oxide paper spots of amino acids are sharp, compact and distinct with no or reduced tailings, which are commonly observed with unimpregnated paper. Further the mixed systems increase the resolving power⁴ and R_f values decrease considerably in comparison of unimpregnated paper. Thus the superiority of the impregnated paper over plain paper is due to high resolving capability and compactness of the spots⁵. It is also observed that in most of the systems R_f values increase with the length of side-chain, i.e. molecular weight of amino acids. Thus the R_f values follow the sequence : leucine > valine > alanine > glycine.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(II) by Extraction of its Cyclohexylthioglycolate Complex with Chloroform

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IRON has been determined spectrophotometrically using some reagents¹. A new method is developed which is simple and sensitive and equally accurate

and may be applied for the determination of iron in certain alloys.

Experimental

Iron(II) solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium ferrous sulphate in dilute sulphuric acid and standardised by known methods². Cyclohexylthioglycolate was prepared by the reported method³. A 0.1% solution of the cyclohexylthioglycolate was prepared in ethanol. Buffer solution of ammonia/ammonium acetate was used to adjust the pH.

Procedure : To an aliquot of sample solution containing 2.18–44.8 μg iron, was added 0.1% cyclohexylthioglycolate (1.5 ml), ammonia buffer (2.0 ml), potassium nitrate solution (1 ml) and chloroform (10 ml). The mixture was shaken gently for 1 min and allowed to settle when two phases separated immediately. The chloroform layer containing the extracted complex was poured on to the anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) to remove the last traces of water. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 520 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of cyclohexylthioglycolate and iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate in chloroform solutions were measured against ethanol and reagents blank respectively.

Extraction of iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate was carried out at different pH values from which the optimum pH range was found to be 8.5–9.2. The extractions were quantitative with 1.0–2.0 ml of the 0.1% reagent solution. In all the cases, 1.5 ml of the reagent was used. It was observed that the absorption remained constant upto 30 ml of the aqueous phase and above this the extraction was not quantitative.

Effects of various electrolytes such as sodium chloride, sodium acetate, potassium chloride and potassium nitrate (0.02–0.6 M) were studied. The extraction was found to be quantitative if the electrolyte concentration was not less than 0.05 M. So 0.1 M potassium nitrate was used in each case.

No change was observed in the extent of extraction when shaking time was varied from 30 s to 2 min; 1 min of shaking was enough for the quantitative extraction of the complex into chloroform.

The composition of iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate was established by Job's method of continuous variation and the mole-ratio method. A sharp peak at 0.67 mole fraction of ligand in Job's curve and a clear break at 1 : 2 metal-cyclohexylthioglycolate ratio in mole-ratio plot suggest the formation of 1 : 2 complex under these conditions.

Calibration curve : With the optimum conditions described above, a calibration curve was constructed for iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate at 520 nm. Beer's law was found to be obeyed over the concentration